

INCENTIVE
CITIZEN SCIENCE HUBS

D2.1

Co-Creation Workshop and its outcomes

University of Twente

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

About this report

INCENTIVE is a 3-year European project aiming to demonstrate the potential of citizen science (CS) through the co-creation, establishment and assessment of Citizen Science Hubs (CSHs) in four European universities:

- University of Twente (NL);
- Autonomous University of Barcelona (ES);
- Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (GR);
- Vilnius Gediminas Technical University (LT).

Among one of its first actions, a **Co-Creation Workshop** was organized to engage with the stakeholders of each RPFO aiming to co-define the pivotal aspects of the governance and operation of the prospective CSHs. The current report presents its approach and the outcomes.

About the Co-Creation Workshop approach

The approach we applied for the Co-Creation Workshop is **Responsible Futuring**. This approach is developed by one of INCENTIVE's partner, University of Twente's DesignLab. DesignLab aims to bridge the gap between society and science and opening up new avenues to tackle societal challenges, which is in line with the aims of INCENTIVE. By integrating values, norms, and ethical perspectives in the co-design process, Responsible Futuring provides a suitable framework to develop tailored governance and operating models for the CSHs of each RPFO with active roles, incentives, and activities for all R&I stakeholders.

In preparing and delivering the Co-Creation Workshop, we took seven sequential steps that can be summarised as:

- Step 1: Methodology for the Co-Creation Workshop
- Step 2: Co-Creation Workshop programme
- Step 3: Moderation
- Step 4: Preparing the RPFOs and their stakeholders
- Step 5: Accommodating observers to the Co-Creation Workshop
- Step 6: Delivering the Co-Creation Workshop
- Step 7: Aftercare and interim adjustments

Outcomes of the Co-Creation Workshop

The Co-Creation Workshop has provided a baseline design of an RRI-oriented CSH, addressing its governance framework, monitoring and assessment framework, operating model, incentivisation tools and key activities. Its outcomes will provide input to several tasks and deliverables that will follow in the

project, such as defining the governance framework and operating model, its monitoring and assessment framework and its incentivisation tools.

As for the Building Blocks for the CSH, we reported:

Base line design of an RRI-oriented CSH:	<p>Core RRI-based values for the four RPFOS are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AUTH: Learning and Inclusiveness • VGTU: Learning and Inclusiveness • UAB: Responsibility and Inclusiveness/Openness • UT: Openness
Pivotal aspects of its governance framework and operating model	The CSH is a go-to place for citizens and researchers to work together on challenges. It offers training in methods, skills and a joint way of working.
Addressing the Monitoring and Evaluation framework	INCENTIVE's impact areas are the six RRI keys and economic growth . These were translated into core RRI-based values and how these would affect the success of the CSH. As a follow up, elements of success per preferred CSH will be defined.
Addressing incentivisation tools	<p>Major ways to incentivise with stakeholders were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Be clear on what to expect • Make the participants feel comfortable • Relate to intrinsic interest of the stakeholders
Addressing key activities	<p>The main clusters of clusters that have been addressed are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research • Awareness & engagement: • Education

As for the Outcomes per RPFOS, we reported:

AUTH	<p>Key stakeholders represent academia and civil society; government and public sector are limitedly present. The main (clusters of) activities include Lifelong Learning, Data Collection, Participatory Science and Partnerships. To realise this, partnerships are foreseen with local and regional partners and national and EU funding. Turning these (clusters of) activities into operational nodes, ethics, involving citizen and supporting CS communities are at its core.</p>
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VGTU	<p>Key stakeholders represent academia and the private sector; government and civil society are absent or limitedly present. The main (clusters of) activities include Research, Awareness & Engagement, Agenda Setting and Training & Education. To realise this, the CSH is aiming to include “everyone”, yet, this diversity is also considered to be challenging bringing up communication issues and conflicting views. Also, a potential lack of interest by both scientists and citizens is considered and structural changes are needed in funding and training. Turning these (clusters of) activities into operational nodes, Training, CS Skills and Awareness & Engagement are at its core.</p>
UAB	<p>Key stakeholders represent academia, government and civil society; the private sector is absent. The main (clusters of) activities include Defining Challenges between UAB and Quadruple Helix, Engagement with Stakeholders and Engaging with New CS Researchers. This can be done through training, network development, coordination, tool provision and sharing good practices of existing CS projects. Turning these (clusters of) activities into operational nodes, CS project support, CS online tools & spaces, Communication & Dissemination and Training & Education are at its core.</p>
UT	<p>Key stakeholders represent academia, government, private sector and civil society – so all Quadruple Helix quadrants. The main (clusters of) activities concern providing support to citizens. More specifically, support should be provided on scientific methods and proving solutions for practical matters for citizens. To realise this, the CSH needs an infrastructure connected to existing social. Turning these (clusters of) activities into operational nodes, Communication & Dissemination are at its core.</p>

Conclusions

Putting the approach in practice in the Co-Creation Workshop, several needs from the project could not be met with the Responsible Futuring approach. Main concerns were *I) Ownership vs. level of abstraction, II) Multiple targets in one remote setting, III) Variety of participants, cultures and languages, IV) Responsible futuring and the Responsible Futuring approach are recent developments, and V) How to best support meaningful regional discussion?*

The insights generated by the Co-Creation Workshop are input for the next steps in the project being:

1. Defining the Monitoring and Assessment Framework (T4.1);
2. Detailing the respective Governance Frameworks and Operations Models of each RPFO's CSH (T2.2);
3. Defining Incentivisation Tools for Engaging with Stakeholders (T2.3) and;
4. Defining per RPFO what the activities of their CSH should be (T2.4).

All of this will be essential input to prepare for the pilots at each of the RPFOs that are intended for 2022.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 About INCENTIVE

Europe's Research Performing and Funding Organisations (RPFOS) have a crucial role to play as agents of institutional change towards firmly grounding Responsible Research Innovation (RRI) in our society. The successful fulfilment of this challenging, yet highly significant role, calls for the values of RRI to be well-embedded into their governance, as well as their operation with greater and more systematic participation of citizens and all R&I stakeholders. The 3-year European project INCENTIVE (Grant Agreement No 101005330) mobilises citizens and stakeholders to become agents of scientific change through their direct participation. At the same time, the participating institutes and universities are guided to open their doors to citizens and equip them with the necessary tools for enhanced scientific skills. Our ambition is to **co-create CSHs (CSH) for a new generation of citizen scientists and a new institutional European paradigm that bridges science with society.**

INCENTIVE aims to demonstrate the potential of citizen science (CS) through the co-creation, establishment and assessment of CSHs in four RPFOS (see **Fig 1**):

- University of Twente (NL);
- Autonomous University of Barcelona (ES);
- Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (GR);
- Vilnius Gediminas Technical University (LT).

By doing so, the project accelerates the transition of these institutions to a more inclusive, open and democratic innovation and scientific governance, under the principles of RRI. We tailor the governance and operating models of these hubs to their unique institutional specificities and regional ecosystems of R&I stakeholders, before putting them to the test to drive institutional change through a series of RRI-grounding actions conducted with and for society (CS, co-creation of public policies, R&I agenda setting, etc.).

1.2 About the Co-Creation Workshop

Among one of the project's first actions, a **Co-Creation Workshop** was prepared and organized to engage with the stakeholders of each RPFOS. The aim of this task was to co-define the pivotal aspects of the governance and operation of the prospective CSHs. We did this in an online workshop in collaboration with our key stakeholders while applying DesignLab's Responsible Futuring approach that is explained in Section 2. The results of this task form the input for the tasks that deal with the governance frameworks and operating models as well as the activities of each CSH, preparing incentivisation tools to engage with stakeholders and co-creating the project's Monitoring and Evaluation Framework.

1.3 About this report

This report describes the methodology and outcomes of the Co-Creation Workshop for the baseline design of an RRI-oriented CSH, addressing its governance framework, monitoring and assessment framework, operating model, incentivisation tools and key activities. After this introduction, **Section 2** details the Co-Creation Workshop process step by step, from its methodology to how it was executed. **Section 3** covers the outcomes of the Co-creation Workshop both related to the building blocks of an RRI-oriented CSH as well as per RPFO. To this section, we added findings of a thematic analysis on the workshop outcomes, and we explain what we have learned from preparing and running the Co-Creation Workshop. Finally, **Section 4** completes the report outlining its conclusions.

Figure 1: Distribution of INCENTIVE's pilot RPFOs across Europe

2. ABOUT THE CO-CREATION WORKSHOP APPROACH

2.1 Step 1: Methodology for the Co-Creation Workshop

2.1.1 *Responsible Futuring as approach for co-creation in INCENTIVE*

INCENTIVE has the goal to foster **Responsible Research and Innovation** (RRI) in research institutions. Instead of focusing only on the scientists and academics, INCENTIVE promotes collaboration with all relevant societal actors by establishing sustainable transdisciplinary hubs for stimulating and supporting excellent CS with engaged roles for all Research and Innovation (R&I) stakeholders. To achieve this goal, we need an approach that incorporates RRI values with transdisciplinary practices. Many society-centred and responsible innovation approaches share a focus on responsible design, incorporating theories and frameworks from philosophy of technology. However, they do not include **stakeholders as partners** in the design process. Furthermore, other approaches and frameworks have a transdisciplinary focus, yet they do not enable fully critical co-creation, co-design, co-imagination focusing on decision making processes rather than shaping processes.

The approach we used for the Co-Creation Workshop is **Responsible Futuring**, which offers a combination of transdisciplinary practices, responsible design and co-design with societal stakeholders that makes it uniquely positioned to enable responsible co-creation, enabling reflection about values and ethical implications. This approach was developed by one of INCENTIVE's partner, University of Twente's DesignLab, aiming to bridge the gap between society and science and opening up new avenues to tackle societal challenges, which is in line with the aims of INCENTIVE.

Responsible Futuring 'raises above' other approaches for co-creation (e.g., classic Design Thinking) by integrating values, norms, and ethical perspectives in the process, stimulating reflection, and focusing on symmetrical collaboration and co-construction. It enables complex problem framing while giving agency to stakeholders, rather than only empathizing with them. Decision-making is done with stakeholders too, who not only have a say, but they are also co-owners. The approach enables stakeholders to engage with different worldviews, expertise and values and finds a productive synthesis, a shared outlook. Hence, Responsible Futuring provides a suitable framework to develop tailored governance and operating models for the CSHs of each RPFO with active roles, incentives, and activities for all R&I stakeholders.

The stakeholders' societal needs, values, and requirements will drive the co-creation of the framework to establish the CSHs through our Responsible Futuring approach. Since the approach goes further than existing design thinking methods, it is applied to co-design concepts of CSH that also includes societal values, norms, and behaviours of the different stakeholders involved. Stakeholders are enabled to join forces, making thoughts and ideas tangible to support sense-making, ideate together with moral imagination, promoting citizen ethics and value change. In practice, this means that responsible solutions are developed and designed by all the stakeholders - citizens included -, which are societal actors belonging

to one of the Quadruple Helix clusters (i.e., academia, industry, civic society and governmental organization).

Responsible Futuring consists of iterative phases that allow for multiple methods to be applied depending on the stakeholders we are working with. Figure 2 explains how the Responsive Futuring-approach was applied for the Co-Creation Workshop. Within INCENTIVE the aim is to co-design concepts and ideas that reflect societal values, norms, and behaviours. Stakeholders - including citizens and communities - have valuable expertise; they are experts. Instead of solely engaging stakeholders, we actively involved them to become co-owners of the societal challenge.

Figure 2 Responsible Futuring-approach applied for the Co-Creation Workshop

So as to effectively deliver the Co-Creation Workshop, we planned to focus on the first three phases of Responsible Futuring, namely Connect and Relate, Understand and Frame, and Imagine and Ideate. Below, we introduce a breakdown of the envisioned goals, outcomes and ways of working in the sessions. As the present COVID-19 restrictions prevented traveling and physically bringing together the different RFOs and their stakeholders, the workshop was offered as an online workshop. It was divided into the different stages and spread over various days to be able to guarantee a close involvement of the participants and their ability to contribute as effective as possible. During the workshop, we made sure to be as inclusive as possible in terms of cultural and language level. While the workshop was mainly held in English, we made sure that participants could express themselves in their own language.

2.1.2 Co-creating CSHs in three phases

Prework

We incorporate the Responsible Futuring approach in the Co-Creation Workshop as the primary vehicle of co-reflection and to lay the foundation to co-design and co-create a CSH baseline. Considering WP1 findings and preliminary discussions with WP2 partners and supporting partners, the first months were used to prepare the workshop. In the preparation stage, preliminary context mapping was conducted in which we merged the knowledge of WP1 with a stakeholder analysis in which all RPFs were asked to identify their key stakeholders and indicate their levels of involvement in their preferred CSH. We made sure to grasp and consider the cultural and local context of the identified stakeholders. To this end, a preliminary selection was made of societal challenges that each CSH is interested in tackling and we mapped out the stakeholders to be involved in the workshops and identified societal challenges to tackle locally. The results of this preliminary stage work (“Prework”) were made available in an online white board (see Appendix 3 – Part I).

Connect & Relate: a session on mapping to co-create and roads to collaboration

In the first Connect and Relate phase, it is fundamental to bring together stakeholders and enable their collaboration. The focus is on three aspects of transdisciplinary collaboration. First, we engage with worldviews, i.e., how each stakeholder makes sense of the world, her views on human-technology relationships, society, and innovation. We engage in and understand value dynamics, i.e., which values stakeholders find essential, how they conceptualize them, what actions they take to embed those values in practice. Second, we develop common ground, i.e., finding a way to communicate and understand each other even when having different perspectives. Third, we co-develop transdisciplinary workflows and exchange way of working. It is a phase to nurture team building and engage with stakeholders' views coming from various disciplines. The main output is a concrete plan to connect expertise and awareness in the team.

Connect & Relate will be covered in the first session. In this session, we will kick-off and enable the collaboration between project partners and stakeholders identified in the preparation effort. We support the participants to communicate their views, standpoints, and values. We do not limit ourselves to discussions: we visualize and make each other perspectives tangible. In doing so, it is easier to create a map and roads to enable collaboration. We deem this activity as fundamental to creating the necessary ground for a successful collaboration.

Outline for Session I:

Who	RPFs and their key stakeholders
What	Session to surface each other values and relate them to each other perspectives and way of working. The workshop is meant to make explicit expertise, principles, and methods and highlight connection, frictions, and opportunities. Tangible outcomes are a visualized map of values, perspectives, and a way of working. The outcome of this session will represent the groundwork for

	the following sessions.
Why	Nurture team building and engage with stakeholders' perspectives coming from various disciplines, expertise, and methods. It lays the groundwork on the CS Hubs, governance framework, community building, activities of the Hubs, monitoring and assessment framework, etc.
How	Using techniques from critical design to help the participants express their point of view. The methods enable us to go beyond mere discussion and to visualize positions literally, the map of values, perspective and ways of working. And to visually identify a road to collaboration. What will the participants do? Design fiction-inspired exercises (i.e., letters to future self), tangible sense-making exercises, and building maps and roads.

Understand & Frame: a session on framing governance and operations

The essence of the second Understand and Frame phase is to have an in-depth understanding of the challenge, the context, and the people. In Understand and Frame, a transdisciplinary team goes through a series of research and design-oriented activities to gain knowledge and develop a shared frame. The focus is on the following aspects: to understand issues, dynamics, people, context, values, norms, i.e., gain an in-depth knowledge of all relevant facets of the challenge and consider the implications the challenge has on the future; We map the acquired knowledge, i.e., make sense of the acquired knowledge by systematizing it and reflect on it from multiple perspectives. Define patterns, relationships, and themes; We develop a Transdisciplinary Frame, i.e., formulate an actionable proposal that utilizes the emerging relationship and themes. The activity is geared towards producing a coherent set of statements to think with and act from a techno-moral perspective.

Understand & Frame will be covered in the second session, where the goal is to develop a common frame among partners and stakeholders. We actively work to have a shared pair of lenses to look at the CSHs creation. The second session helps participants tangibly declare how they will tackle bringing the CSHs to life, considering the values, perspectives and ways of working mapped in the previous session.

Outline for Session II:

Who	RPFOs and their key stakeholders
What	Session to find a common frame about CS Hubs. The session is meant to incorporate WP1 results; and the previous workshop insights to find a common way to establish CS Hubs, governance, and policy. We elaborate on societal challenges, stakeholders' position in the hub and elaborate on CS principles. Output is a visualized tangible frame.
Why	A frame is an actionable set of statements that defines how we look at CS Hubs. It is a productive way to start imagining how to set them up.

How	We will work tangibly to surface each other standpoint. We will use scenario-based techniques and gamification to facilitate the process. Participants will be involved in serious games and scenario-based design activities.
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Imagine & Ideate: exploring future scenarios of CSHs

The third **Imagine & Ideate** phase is the most generative phase of the approach. In this phase, the focus is on imagining the future and ideating it tangibly. Hence, transdisciplinary teams will engage in tangible futuring exercises to develop and reflect future scenarios, i.e., visualize how future situations, issues and dynamics can be; prototype current and future values, i.e., imagining and making low-fi prototypes according to values and taking moral stances into account; and ideate, evoke and provoke reflections through making, i.e., imagining and ideating speculatively to reflect about the implications of ideas.

Imagine & Ideate will be covered in the third and last session in which we combine what we have learned in the previous ones to imagine concretely how the CSHs will look like, their governance, and policies. This is the time to visualize and make tangible our desirable future for the CSHs. We will hone in on the dynamics between the CSHs, the stakeholders, and the local society. We will imagine the CSHs with moral imagination: we will discuss ethical implications, how values will change and shape dynamics. This session is the grand finale of the Co-Creation Workshop, providing a tangible and reflective concept of CSHs.

Outline for Session III:

Who	RPFOs and their key stakeholders
What	Considering the previous sessions, we will build future scenarios incorporating values, ways of working, perspectives, and a shared frame. We will reason on dynamics and societal challenges. We will co-create a tangible representation of CS Hubs, its governance, and policy; then, we will reflect on the hubs' socio-ethical implications and the hubs' socio-ethical implications.
Why	Future Based Scenario ideated with moral imagination. Make conversations and discussions visualized and tangible. They help to act and reflect on dynamics and implications.
How	We will continue to use scenario-based techniques. Participants will be involved in a narrative-based tangible scenario activity, plus analytical activities of desirable futures back-casting.

2.2 Step 2: Co-Creation Workshop programme

During this step, the Organising Team (staff and students) at DesignLab prepared a programme for the Co-Creation Workshop to cover the main questions on the required output, alignment with the methodology and to lay a proper baseline for **stakeholder engagement and co-ownership** by each of the four RPFOs. This step also included the creation of a first online white board of regional profiles that the RPFO contacts were asked to further elaborate upon. We decided to spread the Co-Creation Workshop across **several**

online sessions due to the COVID-19 restrictions throughout Europe. This put extra pressure on the schedule several sessions of the same workshop had to be planned. We managed to hold two out of the three sessions prior the 2021 summer break. The last and final session took place after the summer, which also conveniently allowed the participants to take some time to ideate on their preferred CSH.

According to the project plan, the members of the **Advisory Board** (AB) were supposed to be involved from the beginning. However, since the installation of the AB was delayed because of COVID-19, it's members were not, yet, available during the preparations of the workshop nor could they join the sessions that took place before the 2021 summer break. Instead, they were consulted and asked for feedback on the full draft of this report to make sure we did include their knowledge and skills.

2.3 Step 3: Moderation

Moderation was prepared and delivered by a **skilled moderator** from DesignLab with a track record in facilitating multistakeholder co-creation processes. This lead moderator was supported by a technical moderator who prepared and oversaw the digital environment for each session in case participants were facing technical difficulties. As most of the co-creation took place in the sub sessions, moderation here was carefully prepared by the lead moderator, although we identified and instructed **local hosts** to run the regional discussions. In each of the digital rooms, local hosts were moderating the regional discussions while being supported by a **technical host** who joined the room and the digital white board to provide technical support as well as making notes on the digital white board. The local hosts were representatives of the respective RPFO, so that the regional discussion was led by a familiar face who also had a stake in the regional discussion. Prior to the sessions, the local hosts were instructed on the programme and exercises for the upcoming session in a **bilateral premeeting**. For each session, a **session protocol** was made that explained the programme in detail including the instructions per exercise to support the discussions (see Appendix II).

2.4 Step 4: Preparing the RPFOs and their stakeholders

We shared our preparatory steps with the four RPFOs that needed to identify their (preferred) participants and prepare the sessions in their own ecosystems. We suggested that the RPFO contacts informally check with their stakeholders whether all instructions were clear and for them be contacted in case of need, assuming that these local contacts were more in direct contact with their stakeholders.

These are the steps we took to inform the RPFOs and their stakeholders:

1. Providing guidelines to the RPFOs on who their preferred participants could be. We were supposed to gather a representative group of stakeholders to participate and to be informed prior and during the workshop. The RPFO contacts shared the contact details of their preferred participants with us;
2. Onboarding the participants was done centrally as we considered them as one group. The participants were addressed in English in several e-mails explaining them what we were planning to

- do and when their availabilities would be required. Based on the majority of votes, the dates of 16 and 23 June 2021 were set as the first dates for the sessions;
3. An **Onboarding Kit** was shared two weeks prior to the session to provide the participants with the necessary background, preparations and practicalities such as URLs. We made two Onboarding Kits: one for 16-23 June and one for 22 September. As an example, the 22 September 2021 Onboarding Kit is attached to this report. INCENTIVE’s consortium partner White Research made a tailored design for it, using the project’s house style;
 4. **Reminders** were sent close to the actual dates of the sessions to enthuse the participants. Via these reminders, we asked the participants to submit their Informed Consent Form and to prepare for the session by completing minor homework exercises.

We decided to communicate centrally to ensure consistency in the preparations and conclusions of each session.

2.5 Step 5: Accommodating observers to the Co-Creation Workshop

As the Co-Creation Workshop served many different tasks in the project, we decided make accommodations for the participation of observers to the Co-Creation Workshop, so that they could join the plenary parts of the workshop as well as the online rooms where the stakeholders per university were working on their exercises. Joining the session as an observer gave them the opportunity to experience the interaction and co-creation process and browse through the supporting Mural board that we have made. These observers – from ECSA, CC-CS, Q-Plan and WR – were instructed on their role and how to join the session without interfering with the co-creation process. They were muted by default and with their cameras on. They could move around the plenary observatory and share observations with other observers or step in one of the rooms to observe. Observers were asked not to add to Mural boards, and we did not ask for an Informed consent form as they were not contributing to the co-creation process.

2.6 Step 6: Delivering the Co-Creation Workshop

The Co-Creation Workshop ran as co-creation process spread across three online sessions that required specific tools for communicating and co-creation. We used various tools to achieve the goals of each session as is shown in Table 3.

Table 3 Overview of the aims and tools of the Co-Creation Workshop

Phase	Aims	Tools
Prework	Reach a common notion on the regional societal challenges, research areas and stakeholders, as context for the regional CSH.	Playground 1 and 2 (Mural): prework canvas

Phase	Aims	Tools
Connect & Relate	Getting to know each other and reach a common notion of CS	Playground 1 (Mural): self-portraits, Why, How & What and Role Play
Understand & Frame	Reach a common notion of your CSH by understanding main stakeholder(s)	Playground 2 (Mural); Empathy Map, Value Proposition Canvas
Imagine & Ideate	Reach a common notion of how values shape your CSH	Playground 3 (Mural); Scenario building, reflection, preferable future, main activities

The sessions took place online, using **Zoom** to interact. The participants received the login details in advance and were invited to join 15 minutes earlier to check their connection, allow automated updates and give them time to ask questions to the organizing team prior to the session. Zoom allowed us to divide the participants across several rooms that we had previously set up: Observatory, Twente, Thessaloniki, Barcelona and Vilnius.

We used **Mural** to prepare online working spaces where participants could work on remotely and outside of the sessions. The INCENTIVE playgrounds Part 1, Part 2 and Part 3 were prepared to support the participants during the online sessions and to capture the main outcomes of their discussions regarding the major steps of designing their preferred CSH together. The Mural boards were carefully prepared by the Organising Team at DesignLab consisting of the moderator, Responsible Futuring researchers, programme manager and a Master student with visualisation skills. Major requirements for the boards were to accommodate interaction and co-ownership (which is why we made working spaces per hub), a recognisable look and feel (which is why we included the house style of the project) and a way to connect the different stages and exercises of the sessions (which is why we included the accompanying sections of the **Responsible Futures Fig 2**, p.12). The Mural boards were made available prior to each session, so that the participants could familiarise themselves, read in and contribute by adding relevant background materials and sharing their homework exercises. The INCENTIVE playgrounds are available online and as downloads in Mural. Downloads (dated 30 September 2021) are added as appendices to this report (see Appendix III).

At the top of the first playground, for every RPFO a **Prework** section was prepared that captured a baseline profile of each region to ensure a common frame at the start of the co-creation process. A team of UT students prepared the prework session in close collaboration with the RPFOs. Based on desk research, initial answers were formulated per RPFO regarding the following:

1. What is special about your region? What are commonly recognised (societal) challenges of your region?;

2. Identify stakeholders: Who are CS champions from society [in your region]? What are the barriers for citizen to connect with science [in your region]? What are the enablers for citizens to connect with society [in your region];
3. What are the enablers for researchers to connect with society? What are the barriers for researchers to connect with science? Who are CS champions from science?;
4. What research areas are well presented at your university?

The answers were checked with the RPOs and then brought to Playground 1 to be accessed by the key stakeholder from the respective regions for further elaboration. A stakeholder map was made showing the level of involvement of the various stakeholders that were identified. Finally, some visual materials were added to represent the region (e.g., a landscape, logo, a map).

2.6.1 Connect & Relate

In the first session, on June 16th, 2021, we focused on **Connect** (getting to know each other) & **Relate** (understanding one another's perspectives, discussing frictions and issues). In this session, participants explored their role as actor - modest or leading - in the Citizen Science Hub of their region. Another focus point was to understand and consider one another's motives and values. The playground for this first session was fully dedicated to Connect and Relate. Prior to and during this session, supportive tailor-made exercises aimed to reveal the needs and capacities in the group (where do you see yourself in the future?) and to reach a general understanding of Citizen Science in the group (why, what and how of Citizen Science as well as a role-playing exercise). By offering different types of exercises and focusing on visualisation and interaction, we enabled the participants to all contribute to the discussions and the white board that captured the group's output.

The programme of the first session was:

10:00	Plenary welcome and warming-up Introduction of the 'why' of CS
10:10	CS in a nutshell by Andrea Troncoso (ECSA)
10:20	Creating and exchanging self-portraits: find synergies and frictions Summarise the why, how, and what of CS of your team
11:10	Step into each other's shoes in a real-life CS case
11:35	Future self-portrait & main findings of your team
11:50	Exchanging main findings
12:00	Closing

2.6.2 Understand & Frame

In the second session, on June 23rd, 2021, we focused on **Understand** (define what your CSGH is about and for whom) & **Frame** (define a common frame for your CSH). In this session, the focus was on getting the main stakeholder group participants more closely involved, to understand the incentives of their main stakeholder group regarding being part of the CSH and to define a common frame of their CSH. A value proposition was used to support the discussion.

The playground supported the second session that was fully dedicated to Understand & Frame. In this session, the participants were brought together to reach a common understanding of their preferred CSH. At the top of the playground, the Prewrite was again added, and some time was allocated to revisit and refine this part of the online working space. The participants were asked to prioritise local challenges, research topics and stakeholders. This resulted in more focus for the preferred CSH that the participants were going to formulate in the upcoming phases of the co-creation process. Tailor-made exercises aimed to allow the participants to analyse one or two stakeholder groups they really wanted to be part of the CSH and define their needs using an empathy map. Together with the priorities indicated in the prework, this was further developed into a value proposition of the preferred CSH explaining its insights, promise, benefits and proofs for the respective stakeholder group. A CSH hero was selected to represent the preferred CSH and finally, a 2025 headline was formulated that expressed what the future success of the CSH would look like.

The programme of the second session was:

10:00	<p>Plenary welcome & introduction to the program</p> <p>Co-creating value propositions (as common frame) of your CSH</p> <p>Revisiting pre-work: sharpen contents & identify your main stakeholders</p> <p>From understanding your main stakeholder to main insights for your CSH</p>
11:30	Exchanging main insights: what's similar, what differs across regions
11:45	From insights to promise and proof of your CSH
1:00	<p>Pitching the value propositions of your CSH (5 min. each)</p> <p>Stakeholder panels (across regions) create 'futuring' feedback</p> <p>Feedback round</p> <p>Preview next session on 22nd September & homework</p>
2:00	Closing

2.6.3 *Imagine & Ideate*

In the third session, on September 22nd, 2021, we focused on **Imagine** (what will your preferred CSH look like?) & **Ideate** (how can this be put in practice?). At the end of the session, we co-defined the pivotal aspects of the governance and operating of the preferred CSH by each RPF0. This was done through meaningful exercises in which participants defined the values of the CSHs, built future scenarios for these, and finally defined the operational nodes of each CSH.

The programme of the third session was:

10:00	Plenary welcome & introduction to the program
10:10	Scenario building based on the selection of main values for your CSH
10:45	Critical reflection of pros and cons of embracing certain values
11:00	Shaping a preferable future of your CSH
11:25	Sketching main activities of your CSH and indicating how these are performed
11:50	Follow-up and closure
12:00	Closing

The aim of the supporting Playground 3 was to define the key values and main activities of the ideal CSH, and thus provide a baseline for the governance and operating of the four envisaged CSHs. Tailor-made exercises aimed to reveal the RRI-based values that the participants were attributing to the CSH and how their key values would affect the operating of the future CSH. Turning values into concrete operations, the participants concluded this phase by defining three (clusters of) activities for the ideal CSH and arranging these in such a way to illustrate how it would relate to the core activities of the CSH and if it would be more university or society driven, and hence how it should be operated. With that, the third playground concluded the Co-Creation Workshop.

2.7 Step 7: Aftercare and interim adjustments

After each session, we sent an e-mail to all participants and observers, thanking them for their time and input, summarising what we had done and explaining the next steps in the co-creation process. This way, we consistently reached all parties involved, shared information (references, URLs) and expressed our appreciation of the efforts all participants put in.

In between the sessions, we met individually with the RPFO contacts for intermediate reflection and feedback, and to prepare for the next session. We made sure to emphasize frequently that the organising team was always available for questions and comments. In between sessions, we were once asked to support with Mural technicalities, and we received information from participants on their availability for upcoming sessions. No questions were received on the process or content of the Co-Creation Workshop.

Between the first and second session, some adjustments were made to better support the co-creation process in each of the sub sessions and to allow for more interaction by the following means:

- More plenary explanation on what to do and why;
- Explanation within the groups by local hosts from each respective RPFO;
- More room for dialogue and co-creation: more time, less assignments;
- More exchange between the regions, especially in the second session.

3. OUTCOMES OF THE CO-CREATION WORKSHOP

3.1 Building blocks for the CSH

3.1.1 Baseline design of an RRI-oriented CSH

In Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), values have a more explicit role compared to ‘regular’ research and innovation. As the CSH in INCENTIVE are to be RRI-oriented, we gave values (i.e., those related to the RRI-keys) a central role in the Co-Creation Workshop (especially Session III). Participants were asked to select two values and elaborate, in a scenario building exercise, on what these values would entail for their future CSH. Additionally, they were asked to reflect upon the pros and cons of embracing these values. This has led to a baseline design that considers all RRI key areas with most values attributed to ethics and social inclusion and environmental welfare (Table 4)

Table 4: Core RRI-based values that were selected in the Co-Creation Workshop

RRI key areas	CSH values
Economic growth	Growth
Ethics	Responsibility, respect, honesty, integrity
Societal engagement	Responsibility
Gender equality	Inclusiveness, equality
Open access/open science	Openness, inclusiveness, accountability
Science education	Authority, learning, leadership, inclusiveness
Sustainability, social justice, social inclusion	Fairness, justice, environmental welfare, inclusiveness

When selecting their core RRI-based value for their CSH, the four RPFOS respectively prioritized:

- **AUTH:** Learning and Inclusiveness
- **VGTU:** Learning and Inclusiveness
- **UAB:** Responsibility and Inclusiveness/Openness
- **UT:** Openness

3.1.2 Pivotal aspects of its governance framework and operating model

Turning values into concrete operation, the participants concluded the Co-Creation Workshop by defining three (clusters of) activities for the ideal CSH. Participants were asked how these activities would ideally be performed by answering questions such as ‘who is/are in the lead’, ‘who is/are funding’, ‘what area(s) of expertise is/are involved’. Also, they were asked to arrange these activities in such a way to illustrate how a cluster of activities would relate to the core activities of the CSH and if a cluster of activities would be more university or society driven. With these assignments, participants laid the groundworks for the governance framework and operating model of their CSH. The main pivotal aspects are shown below (Table 5). These aspects are explained more in detail per RPFO in Section 2.2.

Table 5: Pivotal aspects of the governance frameworks and operating models for each preferred CSH

RPFO	Key stakeholders*				Cluster of Activities	How to perform	Operational nodes
	A	G	PS	CS			
AUTh	X	(x)	(x)	X	Lifelong Learning, Data Collection, Participatory Science and Partnerships	Local and regional partnerships; national and EU funding	Ethics, involving citizen and supporting CS communities
VG TU	X		(x)	X	Research, Awareness & Engagement, Agenda setting and Training & Education	Including “everyone” Structural changes needed in funding and training	Training, CS skills and Awareness & Engagement
UAB	X	X		X	Defining Challenges between UAB and Quadruple Helix, Engagement with Stakeholders and Engaging with new CS researchers	Training, network development, coordination, tool provision and sharing good practices of existing CS projects	CS project support, CS online tools & spaces, Communication & Dissemination and Training & Education
UT	X	X	X	X	Providing support to citizens on scientific methods and providing solutions for practical matters for citizens	Need of an infrastructure connected to existing social structures such as libraries	Communication & Dissemination

From the Co-creation Workshop outcomes, a general picture emerges of a go-to place for citizens with societal questions that require a scientific method and who want to contribute to evidence-based research

using participatory designs resulting in practical solutions. For researchers, the CSH is a go-to place to work on challenges with societal stakeholders, where agenda-setting and engagement activities take place and where new researchers in citizen science can meet. The CSH is also the go-to place for training in methods, skills and a joint way of working.

3.1.3 Addressing the Monitoring and Evaluation framework

The Monitoring and Evaluation Framework (Task 4.1 in the project) will be based on defining success in so called 'impact areas'. The impact areas as defined in INCENTIVE are the six RRI keys and economic growth, summing up: societal engagement, open access, ethics, gender equality, science education, sustainability/social justice/social inclusion, ecosystem governance and economic growth/employment/work. In the Co-Creation Workshop, we used these same impact areas and asked participants to select core RRI-based values related to these impact areas (see Table 4). Also, the scenario building exercise in which participants were prompted to consider how their key RRI-values would affect the success of the CSH (e.g., with the question 'what matters most to those involved in the hub') forms a relevant starting point for the Monitoring and Evaluation Framework. The participants of the Co-Creation Workshop have been invited to fill in a dedicated Mural board of defining elements of success as a follow-up to the workshop. All four RPFOS have completed this exercise.

3.1.4 Addressing incentivisation tools

In preparing and delivering the Co-Creation Workshop, we were in direct contact with the regional stakeholders to allow them to prepare and engage as much as possible. Major ways to incentivise with the regional stakeholders prior and during the Co-Creation Workshop were:

- **Being clear on what to expect:** providing clarity on the workshop, its aims, background and organisation. We handled this by preparing an Onboarding Kit (Appendix II);
- **Making the participants feel comfortable:**
 - By following a methodology that aimed to realise a co-creation workshop as a sense-making co-creation process considering the needs and backgrounds of the participants coming from different countries, with different backgrounds and with different levels of familiarity with CS;
 - By involving the contact persons of each RPFOS as much as possible and thus limiting the distance between the workshop participants as much as possible. The identification of the participants occurred via the RPFOS. In between sessions, we reached out to the RPFOS contact persons to explain the upcoming session and we invited them to co-moderate the workshop. We also asked them to reach out to their stakeholders to check their availability and whether the stakeholders needed clarification;
 - By accommodating regional languages in the Co-Creation Workshop. The central communication with the workshop participants was in English, but during the workshop participants were divided in rooms where they could communicate in their own language. In most cases, moderation was also done in the regional language;
- **Relating to the stakeholders' intrinsic interests:** when identifying and communicating with the stakeholders, we asked the RPFOS contacts to find participants to the Co-Creation Workshop who:

- have a stake in the establishment of the CSH (at one of the) RPFOs (VGTU, UAB, AUPh, UT);
- are stakeholder to one of the RPFOs and could be both internal champions (from T1.2) and external stakeholders (from T1.3) representing the Quadruple Helix;
- ideally would be able to participate in all sessions;
- would be balanced in terms of age, career, gender and background.

In Section 3.5 we will elaborate on an engagement baseline that might also provide useful insights for the development of the project's incentivisation tools.

3.1.5 Addressing key activities

The participants concluded the Co-Creation Workshop by defining main (clusters of) activities for the preferred CSH. In general, the main (clusters of) activities that have been addressed are:

- **Research:** data collection, participatory science, engage with new researchers in CS, scientific methods, contributing to evidence-based research;
- **Awareness & engagement:** stakeholder engagement, partnerships, agenda-setting;
- **Education:** training, lifelong learning, skills, scientific methods, and data collection.

During the Co-Creation Workshop, activities were mainly addressed at CSH level, which is why the outcomes in this area are explained more in detail down below in Section 3.2, reporting on the outcomes per RPFO.

3.2 Outcomes per RPFO

We analysed the contents of the Mural boards to report on the outcomes of the Co-Creation Workshop per RPFO. The following section provides summaries that include interpretations made by us. These outcomes will serve as intermediate input in the continued co-creation process and are subject to change and development.

A total of 32 participants was foreseen for the Co-Creation Workshop, making up a set of gender-balanced selected representatives from the RPFOs (e.g., administrative staff, researchers, etc.) and beyond, representatives of citizens and citizens' associations, Citizen Scientists, businesses, authorities and various experts that have a stake in CS. Below is an overview of the participant distribution over the Quadruple Helix quadrants (Table 5). More details regarding the participants' background is added below as part of the outcomes per RPFO.

Table 5: Overview of the distribution of participants to the Co-Creation Workshop*

RPFO	Academia			Government	Private sector	Civil society
	Research	Support	Students			
AUTh	4	3	0	0	1	1
VG TU	2	1	0	0	1	1
UAB	3	2	2	1	0	2
UT	1	1	0	2	1	1
<i>Totals</i>	<i>8</i>	<i>9</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>5</i>

**) also 8 observers participated from non-RPFO consortium partners, such as White Research, SDA Bocconi, Q-Plan and CC-CS. The Organising Team at UT consisted of 10 staff members and students*

3.2.1 Aristoteles University of Thessaloniki (AUTh)

The region in which the **AUTh** is based, is characterised by its economic, cultural and geographic profile connecting the Balkan and the Mediterranean. It has an ancient heritage and a multicultural community. **Key regional challenges** are: air pollution, urban transport, lack of green public spaces and the homeless population.

As part of the Pework to the Co-Creation Workshop, **barriers were identified that keep researchers from connecting with society as well as citizens from connecting with science.** They are shown below in Figure 6a (snapshots taken from Playground 1).

Figure 6a: ATh's barriers and enablers to connect Science and Society¹

Key CS stakeholders have been identified, both in science and in society, that relate to academia and civil society; government and public sector are limitedly present. Out of the identified stakeholders, a total of **nine** representatives joined ATh as participants in the Co-Creation Workshop: we reported two researchers and five support staff from ATh, one private sector representative and one civil society representative. The participants came from various regional institutions:

- Aristoteles University of Thessaloniki researchers in Data Science, Environmental Informatics, Geo Information and support staff from its Technology Transfer Office;
- Thessaloniki Youth Club for UNESCO;
- OK!Thess, which is Thessaloniki's leading start-up hub and a catalyst for the growth of the local innovation ecosystem.

Having selected **Learning** and **Inclusiveness** as their key RRI-based values for the CSH, the preferable CSH for ATh engages with researchers and society including minorities, elderly, disabled and LGBTQ. Figure 6b shows the elements of two scenarios in which respectively inclusiveness and learning govern ATh's CSH. In these scenarios, main activities are partnerships, education and equal participation in the areas of climate action, inequality, growth and sustainable development). People interact physically and through digital channels and citizens may be sensors, data collectors and data analysts. The CSH plays a role as Innovation Hub, Think Tank and easy access to research.

¹ Unreadable note under "what are the enablers for researchers..." is: "In recent years air pollution, traffic issues and climate change have impacted people's lives. So they are interested to solve them"; unreadable note under "what are the barriers for researchers..." is: "Projects go unreported/uncatalogued, since some professional scientists do not know how to label their work."

Scenario 1

In this scenario, **Inclusiveness** governs the CS hub.

Scenario title: Strength lies in differences not in similarities!

*Participatory hubs in
city and neighbourhoods*

Who are the people involved in the CS hub?

How do people interact in your CS hub?

How do others perceive the CS hub?

What are the types of activities that people carry out at the CS hub?

What is the role that the CS hub plays in the community?

What matters most to those involved in the CS hub?

Scenario 2

In this scenario, **Learning** governs the CS hub.

Scenario title: Never stop learning!

Place images in boxes to answer the question

Who are the people involved in the CS hub?

How do people interact in your CS hub?

How do others perceive the CS hub?

What are the types of activities that people carry out at the CS hub?

What is the role that the CS hub plays in the community?

What matters most to those involved in the CS hub?

Figure 6b: When INCLUSIVENESS and LEARNING govern AUTH's CSH

As for defining the main activities of AUTH's preferred CSH, its main (clusters of) activities include Lifelong Learning, Data Collection, Participatory Science and Partnerships (see Fig 6c containing snapshots from Playground 3). To realise this, partnerships are foreseen with local and regional partners (OK!Thess, AUTH's ELKE and KeDiVim initiatives and the municipality of Thessaloniki) and national and EU funding. Turning these (clusters of) activities into **operational nodes**, it appears that AUTH's preferred CSH has ethics, involving citizen and supporting CS communities at its core (see Fig 6d containing snapshots from Playground 3). Research and training are placed at its society intersection and funding, communication and dissemination as well as providing CS co-creation spaces are all seen as happening at the intersection between the CSH and the university.

Figure 6c: AUTH's preferred CSH's main (clusters of) activities

Figure 6d: AUTH's preferred CSH's operational nodes

3.2.2 Vilnius Gediminas Technical University (VGTU)

The region surrounding VGTU is Lithuania's wealthiest region, with an advanced IT sector and world-leading laser industry, while also being start-up friendly. In socioeconomical terms, the region is affected by migration loss, income disparity and a low level of environmental sustainability.

As part of the Pework to the Co-Creation Workshop, **barriers were identified that keep researchers from connecting with society as well as citizens from connecting with science.**

They are shown below in Figure 7a (snapshots taken from Playground 1). No enablers for researchers to connect with society were recorded.

Figure 7a: VGTU's barriers and enablers to connect Science and Society

Key CS stakeholders that were identified have all joined the Co-Creation Workshop representing academia and the private sector; government and civil society are absent or limitedly present. Out of the identified stakeholders, a total of five representatives joined VGTU as participants in the Co-Creation Workshop: we reported 2 researchers and 1 support staff from VGTU, one private sector representative and one civil society representative. The participants came from various regional institutions:

- Vilnius Gediminas Technical University: a researcher in Social Technologies, the vice dean of the Creative Industries Faculty and the head of its Technology Transfer Office;
- The National Creative and Cultural Industries Association;
- KOG Marketing and Communication Science Institute;
- The Bored Panda start-up collective in Vilnius.

Having selected **Inclusiveness** and **Learning** as the key RRI-based values for its CSH, the preferable CSH for VGTU engages with citizens with different backgrounds, researchers and policy makers. Figure 7b (containing snapshots taken from Playground 3) shows elements of the scenario in which **inclusiveness** governs VGTU’s CSH. In this scenario, people interact on an equal basis and science should involve in the mitigation of citizens’ problems. At the CSH, a common understanding is achieved regarding problems, solutions and the value of CS.

Figure 7b: When INCLUSIVENESS governs VGTU’s CSH

As for defining the main activities of VGTU’s preferred CSH, the **main (clusters of) activities** include Research, Awareness & Engagement, Agenda setting and Training & Education (see Fig 7c containing snapshots taken from Playground 3). While bringing these activities into practice, the CSH is aiming to include “everyone”, yet this diversity is also considered to be challenging bringing up communication issues and conflicting views. Also, a potential lack of interest by both scientists and citizens is considered and structural changes are needed in funding and training. Turning these (clusters of) activities into **operational nodes**, it appears that VGTU’s preferred CSH has Training, CS skills and Awareness & Engagement at its core

(see Fig 7d). Doing research preceded by agenda setting is both happening at the borders of the hub to society as well as the university. Funding, project support, ethics and dealing with data and involving citizen is placed outside of the hub at the intersection between university and society. Preferred facilities of the CSH include IT equipment such as hardware and software, a virtual platform to support the exchange of problems and ideas, project support skills on management, event organisation and communication. Access to expert tools and knowledge is also deemed necessary.

Figure 7b: VGTU's preferred CSH's main (clusters of) activities

Figure 7d: VGTU's CSH's operational nodes

3.2.3 Autonomous University of Barcelona (UAB)

The region in which the **UAB** is based, is characterised by the Catalan culture and identity, its entrepreneurial spirit related to the Southern European economic hub B30, as well as an international mindset. The region’s **societal challenges** are transport & mobility, energy & sustainability as well as resilient communities and the circular economy.

As part of the Prework to the Co-Creation Workshop, **barriers were identified that keep researchers from connecting with society as well as citizens from connecting with science.** They are shown below in Figure 8a (snapshots taken from Playground 1).

Figure 8a: UAB’s barriers and enablers to connect Science and Society

Key CS stakeholders that were identified represent societal as well as academic champions that have joined the Co-Creation Workshop – representing civil society, government and academia. So far, the private sector has not been represented. Out of the identified stakeholders, a total of ten representatives joined UAB as participants in the Co-Creation Workshop: we reported three researchers, two support staff and

two students from UAB, two government representatives and one civil society representative. The participants were coming from various regional institutions:

- Autonomous University of Barcelona researchers in Computer Science, Environmental Science and Technology, and Social Psychology as well as support staff;
- Catalan Association of Public Universities;
- Government of Catalonia;
- CREA public research centre dedicated to terrestrial ecology and territorial analysis.

Having selected **Responsibility** and **Inclusiveness/Openness** as the key RRI-based values for the CSH, the preferable CSH for UAB engages with the UAB Community, libraries and schools as well as Quadruple Helix and the B-30 network. Figure 8b (containing snapshots from Playground 3) shows elements of a combined scenario in which Responsibility and Inclusiveness/Openness govern UAB's CSH. People meet physically and virtually to get to know each other and to engaged in CS together. The CSH is perceived as a participatory as well as social space where one can transform both society and research. Types of activities allow for stakeholder engagement, the exchange of ideas and resources as well as skills and tools, training and co-creation. The preferable CSH plays a role as a facilitation to share resources and to implement a CS stakeholder network, to develop skills and to empower citizens by having access to data. Challenges for the CSH might be researchers' concerns about the methodology to ensure the quality of data, and the fact that some researchers might think that research does not have to be carried out with and for society.

Figure 8b: When RESPONSIBILITY and INCLUSIVENESS/OPENNESS govern UAB's CSH¹

As for defining the main activities of UAB's preferred CSH, **its main (clusters of) activities** are: Defining Challenges between UAB and Quadruple Helix, Engagement with Stakeholders and Engaging with New CS Researchers (see Fig 8c containing snapshots from Playground 3). This can be done through training, network development, coordination, tool provision and sharing good practices of existing CS projects. Turning these (clusters of) activities into **operational nodes**, it appears that UAB's preferred CSH has CS project support, CS online tools & spaces, Communication & Dissemination and Training & Education at its core (see Fig 8d containing snapshots from Playground 3). Most operational nodes aim to provide overviews, of tools, spaces, initiatives, communities and projects that all relate to CS. At the intersection

¹ Note from the local host: The yellow and green colors of the post its do *not* correspond to the respective value

between society and university, the CSH performs shared agenda setting. Training for citizens and the managing of engagement are part of the CSH, but less of a core operation.

Figure 8c: UAB's preferred CSH's main (clusters of) activities

Figure 8d: UAB's CSH's operational nodes

Due to limited availability of its stakeholders, UAB decided not to join the third and last Co-Creation Workshop session on Image & Ideate. Alternatively, they brought together their own stakeholders, and followed the sessions protocol as to ensure to obtain the necessary output that was needed. Its outcomes were recorded on Playground 3 in Mural. It shows an advanced level of co-ownership of the co-creation process that has started with the Co-Creation Workshop.

3.2.4 University of Twente (UT)

The region where the UT is based, is characterised by a strong regional identity, a large manufacturing industry and its cross-border collaboration with Germany. **Societal challenges** that the region faces are its socioeconomical challenges including brain drain and a low-educated workforce, urbanisation and limited geographic accessibility.

As part of the Pework to the Co-Creation Workshop, **barriers were identified that keep researchers from connecting with society as well as citizens from connecting with science.** They are shown below in Figure 9a (snapshots taken from Playground 1).

Figure 9a: UT's barriers and enablers to connect Science and Society

Most **key stakeholders** that have been identified both in society and science, have joined the Co-Creation Workshop covering all four quadrats of the Quadruple Helix: academia, government, private sector and civil society. Of the identified stakeholders, a total of six representatives joined UT as participants in the Co-Creation Workshop: we reported one researcher and one support staff from UT, one government representative, one public sector representative and one civil society representative. The participants came from various regional institutions:

- University of Twente researcher in Geographic Information Science and support staff;
- Province of Overijssel;
- Entrepreneur in health and healthcare;
- Twentse Noabers, a citizen collective interest organisation;
- EnschedeLab initiative connecting students and the City of Enschede.

Having selected **Openness** as the key RRI-based value for the CSH, the preferable CSH for UT engages with “whoever wants” – illiterate people, first line workers, low-economic status people and all those that “never joined a party”. Figure 9b (containing snapshots from Playground 3) shows elements of the scenario in which Openness governs UT’s CSH. In this scenario, people interact informal, low-key, and very transparent. They might be storytelling and sharing videos and not in writing as to allow an open attitude. The perception of the CSH should be that it allows everyone to participate hence a good marketing strategy should be in place. Types of activities include “meet & greet”, walk-in meetings and walk-in research and co-creation. The interaction should already start outside of the CSH. The CSH will offer Q&A, give insights to people and intermediate between different people in society. The CSH will be very inclusive and perspective broadening, but it will be challenging to include all and there might be different ideas on what openness stands for. In a side discussion, the participants touched upon the question if every opinion should matter or only the ones that are scientifically supported – as a CSH “you do not want to end up with climate change deniers only but accommodate different world views”, as was explained by one of the participants.

Figure 9b: When OPENNESS governs UT’s CSH

In defining the main activities of UT's preferred CSH its main (clusters of) activities concern providing support to citizens (Fig 9c containing snapshots from Playground 3). More specifically, support should be provided on scientific methods and proving solutions for practical matters for citizens. Citizens coming to the CSH with questions should have ownership should be committed to work towards solutions. A picture arises of a go-to centre for citizens and to support them engaging with science. Indeed, the Twente team stressed to establish and a citizen-focused science hub aiming to reach out first and foremost to citizens - and not to establish a new scientific hub because "we have so many already". It was agreed that an infrastructure is needed that would facilitate citizens to ask their question and learn about science. It is key to connect this to existing social structures such as libraries. Furthermore, it is important to train on "how to become a scientist" by addressing e.g., formulating a good research question. Also, instruction should be available on scientific methods.

Figure 9c: UT's preferred CSH's main (clusters of) activities

Turning these (clusters of) activities into **operational nodes**, it appears that UT's preferable CSH has Communication & Dissemination at its core (see Fig 9d containing snapshots from Playground 3)). This is considered to directly relate to managing engagement, involving citizens, training and education CS skills, and providing CS co-creation spaces and tools as well as CS project overviews. Doing research was placed outside of the CSH which is the same for support & research as well as engagement – this is a job for society in collaboration with the RPFO and its other high education institutes in the region such as the regional university of applied science. The essence of success of the CSH is its continuity.

Figure 9d: UT's CSH's operational nodes

3.3 Barriers and enablers for CSH

Previously in INCENTIVE, good practices and challenges were documented and reported (D1.1 Landscape and good practices of CS initiatives driven by RPFOS) of CSH initiatives based on an exploratory study. Literature review revealed some key challenges that RPFOS face while performing CS, namely: The amount of CS projects reached; Openness of data, and Funding. These outcomes provided a knowledge base for the design of the CSHs, and it provided insights that fed into the preparation process and outcomes of the Co-Creation Workshop.

Throughout the Co-Creation Workshop, several barriers and enablers for stakeholders were encountered. These have been reported upon per RPFOS in the previous section, and Figure 10 summarises them in one overview.

Figure 10: Barriers and enablers to connect Science and Society from the Co-Creation Workshop (sic)

RPFO	Barriers		Enablers	
	Barriers for citizens to connect with science	Barriers for researchers to connect with society	Enablers for citizens to connect with science	Enablers for researchers to connect with society
AUTh	<p>No structure or incentive to keep them engaged</p> <p>CS is something very new</p>	<p>No structure or guidance</p> <p>Projects go unreported/uncatalogued since some professional scientists do not know how to label their work.</p>	<p>Strong volunteering presence</p> <p>Professional scientists welcome citizen scientists to work on their projects.</p>	<p>There is interest from the side of the professional scientists</p> <p>In recent years air pollution, traffic issues and climate change have impacted people's lives. So, they are interested to solve them</p>
VGTU	<p>Lack of interest in science</p> <p>No partnerships between universities</p> <p>No partnerships between businesses and universities</p> <p>Citizens need a connection between doing science work and the benefits in their lives.</p>	<p>Lack of respect/interest in science</p> <p>Poor citizen engagement</p>	<p>International experts</p> <p>Vilnius is a great place for start-ups (policies and government support)</p>	n/a
UAB	<p>Time constraints</p> <p>Technological challenges</p> <p>Lack of willingness to commit in decision-making processes</p> <p>Academic approaches to challenge-Based learning not fully implemented</p>	<p>Researchers and other actors not aware of the benefits of CS</p> <p>Lack of citizen participation in science</p> <p>Rigid structural legal framework</p> <p>Lack of incentives for researchers to carry out CS</p> <p>The UAB Campus in Bellaterra is not easily accessible for all citizens</p>	<p>Interesting projects for them tackling issues that concerns them</p> <p>Feel empowered to improve their territory</p> <p>Gain of knowledge</p>	<p>Creation of a Community of CS at UAB</p> <p>Share of experience in CS</p> <p>Challenge-Based Learning methodology</p> <p>Active ecosystem of Research and Innovation</p> <p>Improvement of urban space & urban quality of life</p>

RPFO	Barriers	Enablers
		CS as a key element of Horizon Europe

3.4 Lessons learned

In this section, we explain what we have learned from the Co-Creation Workshop both in terms of its process and its outcomes. In Section 2, we described the theoretical approach we had in mind for achieving the envisaged outcomes. In practice, we had to make concessions in terms of participants, location, time, and the scope of the workshop, and it also turned out that several needs in the project could not be met with the Responsible Futuring approach. Hence, not all elements that were introduced in Section 2 were incorporated in the final version of the workshop, while other parts were added. Our concerns in preparing and executing the workshop and how we have accommodated them are shown in the table below (Table 11). These lessons learned might be helpful to all other project members who will be organising workshops in the next stages of INCENTIVE.

Table 11: Concerns and how we dealt with them during the Co-Creation Workshop

Concern	How we dealt with it
<p>I) Ownership vs. level of abstraction</p> <p>Our focus was on co-ownership and engaging with the regional stakeholders: we aimed for impact, not just for achieving the project results. Abstract and highly theory-based exercises do not support co-creation processes – on the contrary they might even block them. Yet, the multiple targets that were set for the Co-Creation Workshop were formulated in abstract terms.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prework to sketch concrete context of the CSH's per region • Introducing Mural workspaces per region • Introducing break-out sessions per region • Including a personal assignment (on own values) in the first online session • Using visualisations and techniques as role play and scenario building steered by concrete questions • Addressing specific regional needs of our contact persons, next to meeting project targets • Emphasising to the stakeholders that the workshops and Mural are to be perceived as instruments for realising their (own) co-creation goals • Emphasising to the stakeholders that the Murals are theirs. • Emphasising to the stakeholders currently involved that they are free (and responsible) to involve other stakeholders, also beyond the scope of this task 2.1
<p>II) Multiple targets in one remote setting</p> <p>The multiple targets that were set for the Co-Creation Workshop (input to T2.2, T2.3, T2.4, WP3,</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Splitting the 'one' co-creation workshop in three shorter co-creation sessions of in total 8 hours (2-4-2).

Concern	How we dealt with it
<p>T4.1 and T6.2) were very hard to all cover in one setting and all remote. Also, next to the project targets, we put effort to address specific regional needs of our colleagues in the INCENTIVE project.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emphasising that the Co-Creation Workshop is part of a larger co-creation process • Emphasising to the stakeholders that the Murals are theirs and that they can continue working with the Mural boards beyond the scope of task 2.1.
<p>III) Variety of participants, cultures and languages</p> <p>We strived to be sensitive to the wide diverse participants from different QH quadrants, cultural backgrounds and languages.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Addressing specific regional needs of our contact persons; • Introducing Mural workspaces per region; • Introducing break-out sessions per region; • Giving option to communicate in own language in the break-out sessions; • Providing technical moderators who spoke the native language and/or who were familiar with the specific culture.
<p>IV) Responsible futuring and the Responsible Futuring approach are recent developments</p> <p>Hence, no example workshops and hardly any example assignments were available at the start.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We used some existing assignments and created many tailor-made assignments; • This gave us the flexibility to combine project targets, regional needs with the Responsible Futuring approach.
<p>V) How to best support meaningful regional discussions</p> <p>Having thoughtful assignments at an online whiteboard does not guarantee sufficiently useful open and inclusive discussions.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preparing sessions with the four regions; • On boarding kits sent around in time; • Having local process moderators and technical moderatos in the break-out sessions; • Emphasising to the stakeholders that the workshops and Mural are to be perceived as instruments for realising their (own) co-creation goals.

3.5 Towards a stakeholder engagement baseline

The Co-Creation Workshop marks the start of a 3-year co-creation process of the CSHs in the four pilot regions. We explained in Section 2 how we involved the university contacts of each RPFO to reach out to their Quadruple Helix stakeholders (Step 4) and how we stayed in touch with the various regional key stakeholders (Step 7) which could be the start of a stakeholder engagement baseline.

This engagement baseline can be developed further **in a practical manner**, such as by moving towards a joint CRM. We drew up lists of names, backgrounds and contact details of the key stakeholders at each RPFO who showed an interest in the CSH being established there, and we recorded their presence. This will serve as input for the Community Managers who will be included in the piloting phase during WP3 and who will be trained by SDA Bocconi as part of T2.3 Manual and Tools for Incentivising and Engaging Quadruple Helix Stakeholders in the CSHs.

Another way to move forward relates to a joint **way of working**. We aimed for a common understanding between the stakeholders who were joining us in the Co-Creation Workshop by creating a way of working and a look and feel that would be recognisable to the stakeholders. The **Onboarding kit, Mural boards and Responsible Futuring approach** can be used (as a source of inspiration) for the next steps in INCENTIVE's co-creation process. We started with regional profiles with and for the RPFOs that continue to be accessible via Mural, even after the workshop, to allow the participants to get more familiar with them.

4. CONCLUSIONS

4.1 Approach

The theoretical approach applied to the co-creation process was **Responsible Futuring**, which is visualised below (Figure 2). The approach provided support for analysing and conceptualizing the preferable CSH for each RPFO, in co-creation with the different stakeholders.

Figure 2: Responsible Futuring-approach applied for the Co-Creation Workshop

When putting the approach into practice in the Co-Creation Workshop, we found that several needs from the project could not be met with the Responsible Futuring approach. Our main concerns were how do deal with I) *Ownership vs. level of abstraction*, II) *Multiple targets in one remote setting*, III) *Variety of participants, cultures and languages*, IV) *Responsible futuring and the Responsible Futuring approach are recent developments* and V) *How to best support meaningful regional discussions*. The ways in which we have dealt with these concerns might be helpful to all other project members who will be organising workshops in the next stages of INCENTIVE.

4.2 Outcomes

The outcomes of the Co-Creation Workshop have been presented in two sections, one on CSH building blocks and one on the RPFOS, so as to effectively sort the outcomes for the different partners that will proceed with the workshops' outcomes.

As for the Building Blocks for the CSH, we reported:

<p>Base line design of an RRI-oriented CSH:</p>	<p>Most RRI-based values were attributed to ethics, social inclusion and environmental welfare. When selecting the core value for their CSH, the four RPFOS prioritized:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AUTH: Learning and Inclusiveness • VGTU: Learning and Inclusiveness • UAB: Responsibility and Inclusiveness/Openness • UT: Openness
<p>Pivotal aspects of its governance framework and operating model:</p>	<p>For all four CSHs, the CSH emerges of a go-to place for citizens with societal questions that require a scientific method, who want to contribute to evidence-based research using participatory designs resulting in practical solutions. For researchers, it should be a go-to place to work on challenges with societal stakeholders, where agenda-setting and engagement activities take place and where new researchers in CS meet. The CSH is also the go-to place for training in methods, skills and a joint way of working.</p>
<p>Addressing the Monitoring and Evaluation framework:</p>	<p>INCENTIVE's impact areas are the six RRI keys and economic growth. In the Co-Creation Workshop these were translated into core RRI-based values and we examined how these would affect the success of the CSH (e.g., with the question 'what matters most to those involved in the hub'). As a follow-up to the Co-Creation Workshop, a dedicated Mural board was created to define the elements of success per preferred CSH.</p>
<p>Addressing incentivisation tools:</p>	<p>Major ways to incentivise with the regional stakeholders prior and during the Co-Creation Workshop were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Being clear on what to expect; • Making the participants feel comfortable; • Relating to the stakeholders' intrinsic interests.
<p>Addressing key activities:</p>	<p>The main clusters of activities that have been addressed are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research; • Awareness & engagement;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education.
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As for the Outcomes per RPFO, we reported:

AUTh	<p>Key stakeholders represent academia and civil society; government and public sector are limitedly present. The main (clusters of) activities include Lifelong Learning, Data Collection, Participatory Science and Partnerships. To realise this, partnerships are foreseen with local and regional partners and national and EU funding. Turning these (clusters of) activities into operational nodes, ethics, involving citizen and supporting CS communities are at its core.</p>
VG TU	<p>Key stakeholders represent academia and the private sector; government and civil society are absent or limitedly present. The main (clusters of) activities include Research, Awareness & Engagement, Agenda setting and Training & Education. To realise this, the CSH is aiming to include “everyone”, yet this diversity is also considered to be challenging bringing up communication issues and conflicting views. Also, a potential lack of interest by both scientists and citizens is considered and structural changes are needed in funding and training. Turning these (clusters of) activities into operational nodes, Training, CS skills and Awareness & Engagement are at its core.</p>
UAB	<p>Key stakeholders represent civil society, government and academia; the private sector is absent. The main (clusters of) activities include Defining Challenges between UAB and Quadruple Helix, Engagement with Stakeholders and Engaging with New CS Researchers. This can be done through training, network development, coordination, tool provision and sharing good practices of existing CS projects. Turning these (clusters of) activities into operational nodes, CS project support, CS online tools & spaces, Communication & Dissemination and Training & Education are at its core.</p>
UT	<p>Key stakeholders UT represent civil society, government, academia and the private sector. The main (clusters of) activities include providing support to citizens. More specifically, support should be provided on scientific methods and proving solutions for practical matters for citizens. To realise this, the CSH needs an infrastructure connected to existing social. Turning these (clusters of) activities into operational nodes, Communication & Dissemination are at its core</p>

4.3 Next steps

Co-defining the pivotal aspects of the governance and operation of prospective CSHs at four RPFOs in all corners of Europe was among the first actions in a 3-year co-creation process aiming to demonstrate the

potential of CS through the co-creation, establishment and assessment of CSHs. The insights generated by this workshop are input for the next steps in the project, namely:

5. Defining the Monitoring and Assessment Framework (T4.1);
6. Detailing the respective Governance Frameworks and Operations Models of each RPFO's CSH (T2.2);
7. Defining Incentivisation Tools for Engaging with Stakeholders (T2.3) and;
8. Defining per RPFO what the activities of their CSH should be (T2.4).

All of this will be essential input to preparing us for the pilots at each of the RPFOs that are intended for 2022.

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Appendix I: Session Plan for Session III on 22 September 2021

WORKSHOP PROTOCOL - 3RD INCENTIVE CO-CREATION WORKSHOP

Date workshop: 22 September 2021

Document status: draft

Goal of the workshop: Work together on the preferred future citizen science hub

Expected workshop outcomes:

1. Vision of a preferable citizen science hub
2. **pivotal aspects of the** Operational model per hub
3. **pivotal aspects of the** Governance framework per hub
4. input to the monitoring and evaluation framework

NB: this session is part of a series of sessions that all together constitute the 8-hour Co-creation workshop

Moderators

- LEAD MODERATOR: STUDENT ASSISTANT 1 to provide technical moderation support (breakout rooms)
- 4 technical moderators for the breakout rooms (**important:** moderators record the session in the breakout rooms):
 - o STUDENT ASSISTANT 2 for UT
 - o STUDENT ASSISTANT 3 for UAB
 - o STUDENT ASSISTANT 4 for AUTH
 - o STUDENT ASSISTANT 5 for VGTU
- 4 local co-moderators for the breakout rooms:
 - o UT CP for UT
 - o UAB CP for UAB
 - o AUTH CP for AUTH
 - o VGTU CP for VGTU

	Mural link: here Link to slides <here>		
Time, length	Activity	Roles - what to do	Software

<p>Prior to the workshop Estimated time: 15 minutes</p>	<p>Step 0- Homework- <i>What's in a value?</i></p> <p>Goal: At home, participants reflect on important values while shaping the future CSH to inform the process of shaping a preferable future.</p> <p><i>Individual activity</i></p> <p><u>Pick a value:</u> From the list provided on mural, participants pick two values that they consider important for their CSH. Drag the value from the provided list to the area of mural called 'visualizing values'.</p> <p><u>Provide answers to the questions:</u> Participants provide with their own words answers to these questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ What does this value mean to you? ○ Why is it important? ○ What does it mean to your CS hub? <p><u>Visualize the value:</u> After providing answers to the questions, participants select an icon or a set of icons visualizing the value.</p> <p>Implementor's tip: It is important to encourage participants to visualize the value because this helps them to make it tangible. The same value might mean different things to different people.</p>	<p>UT sends email with Onboarding Kit incl homework on Sept 7</p>	<p>Mural</p>
<p>10.00-10.10 10 min</p>	<p>Introduction 3rd workshop with slides PLENARY Slides</p>	<p>LEAD MODERATOR</p>	<p>Zoom</p>
<p>10.10-10.45 35 min</p>	<p>Step 1. Scenario building (35 min)</p> <p>Goal: It is 2030. Let's speculate about how your CS hub could turn out to be depending on the values governing it. <i>In breakout rooms- group activity</i></p> <p><u>Share (10 min):</u> Share with others the values that you have identified as important in the exercise you have worked on as part of the homework. Explain what these values mean to you.</p> <p><u>Vote and select two values (5 min):</u> Next, use it as a sticker to place your vote on the values you think best represent your team's CS hub. These values are the ones you have chosen in the homework section. After voting, the two values having most votes will be the ones participants use to build the scenarios.</p>	<p>One facilitator in each of the breakout rooms</p> <p>Important for research: Facilitators record the session in each breakout room</p>	<p>Zoom/Mural</p>

	<p>Drag those values to the circles of the ‘scenario building’ exercise.</p> <p><u>Scenario building- Development Scenario 1 (10 min)</u>- Based on the first value, think of how your future CSH would look like and operate in practice. Provide answers to the following questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Who is involved in the CS hub? ○ What are the types of activities that people carry out at the CS hub? ○ How do people interact at the CS hub in this future? ○ How do others perceive the CS hub in this scenario? ○ What matters most to those involved in the CS hub in this scenario? ○ What is the role that the CS hub plays in the community? <p>For each answer, provide a textual explanation (2-3 sentences) and add an icon that visualizes your answer. You may use an icon of the resource library in the right-hand side.</p> <p>After providing answers to all questions, create a collage representing the CSH of this scenario. To do this, copy and paste the icons you have included in the individual questions and put them together to create an image (think of the ‘beach club’ example).</p> <p>Facilitator’s tip: In this step, it is very important that participants know this is a speculative exercise. They need to stretch the value and ‘exaggerate’ what would happen if that specific value governed the CSH. It is critical, from a facilitator perspective, to encourage that attitude so the scenarios are differentiated and embody the value with clarity.</p> <p><u>Scenario building- Development Scenario 2 (10 min)</u>- Based on the first value, think of how your future CSH would look like and operate in practice. Provide answers to the following questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Who is involved in the CS hub? ○ What are the types of activities that people carry out at the CS hub? ○ How do people interact at the CS hub in this future? ○ How do others perceive the CS hub in this scenario? ○ What matters most to those involved in the CS hub in this scenario? ○ What is the role that the CS hub plays in the community? 	<p>(to be able to get the transcript and store in the cloud instead of locally).</p>	
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	<p>For each answer, provide a textual explanation (2-3 sentences) and add an icon that visualizes your answer. You may use an icon of the resource library in the right-hand side.</p> <p>After providing answers to all questions, create a collage representing the CSH of this scenario. To do this, copy and paste the icons you have included in the individual questions and put them together to create an image (think of the 'beach club' example).</p> <p>Facilitator's tip: In this step, it is very important that participants know this is a speculative exercise. They need to stretch the value and 'exaggerate' what would happen if that specific value governed the CSH. It is critical, from a facilitator perspective, to encourage that attitude so the scenarios are differentiated and embody the value with clarity.</p> <p>Plan B: If more time is needed to build the scenarios, we again emphasize it is a speculative exercise (no decision-making exercise), we advise the participants to either split the group in two groups or (if the group is less than 3 people) focus on one scenario (??) and/or use only short sentences?</p>		
<p>10:45- 11:00 15 min</p>	<p>Step 2. Critical reflection (15 min) Goal: The main goal of this exercise is to identify positive and negative consequences of the scenarios to focus not only on utopian aspects of probable futures, but also on potential roadblocks that need to be taken into account while shaping a preferable future. <i>In breakout rooms- group activity</i> <u>Positive and negative impacts:</u> Reflect on the positive and negative aspects of each scenario. Since each 'advantage has a disadvantage' (and vice-versa), think about the following statements for each scenario:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ What is the most positive aspect of this scenario? What are the negative associated aspects to these advantages? ○ What is the worst aspect of this scenario? What could be potential positive aspects of these disadvantages? <p>Describe these pros and cons in the reflection canvas. Write 2-3 sentences</p> <p>Facilitator's tip: This step is all about thinking critically about the scenarios. To avoid focusing on only positive consequences, it is essential that participants elaborate on the disadvantages as well.</p>	<p>One technical and one local facilitator per breakout room</p>	<p>Zoom Mural</p>

11.00-11.05	BREAK		
11h05-11h25 20min	<p>Step 3. Shaping a preferable future (20 minutes) Goal: Develop a scenario representing a preferable future for your CS hub.</p> <p><i>In breakout rooms</i></p> <p><u>Fill out the blanks:</u> Based on the insights gained from building scenarios 1 and 2, governed by different values, at this stage, participants engage in a worldbuilding exercise through which they can take those elements that they identified as important in steps 1 and 2. To achieve this, they can fill out the blanks of certain statements, focusing on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ People involved in the CS hub ○ Interactions at the CS hub ○ Perceptions of the CS Hub ○ Activities at the CS hub ○ Facilities of the CS hub ○ Role of CS hub for the community ○ What matters most for people involved at the CS hub in a preferable future. <p>- <u>Visualize the scenario:</u> Like for the other exercises, in this step, participants will create a collage to visualize that CS hub in a preferable future. To this end, participants can use the resource library on the right-hand side of the exercise.</p> <p>Facilitator’s tip: This step is all about making concrete a preferable future. It is ok for participants to add several post-its to the world building exercise, and to make sure they use their learnings from the other 2 scenarios and the critical reflection. What’s most important is to make it as concrete and actionable as possible.</p>	One technical and one local facilitator per breakout room	Zoom Mural
11h25-11h45 20 min	<p>Step 4. Operational nodes of your preferred CSH (20 min) Goal: To take a helicopter view and propose the main activities and values of the preferred CSH. It is not about being complete, it is about getting to the essence – right to exist – of the Citizen Science Hub.</p> <p><i>In breakout rooms</i></p> <p><u>Activities:</u> Define the main three (clusters of) activities of your preferable CSH. List these clusters of and indicate how the people of the CSH perform these activities. Prompting questions related to the HOW are:</p>		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ How are the preferable values reflected in the activities? ○ Who is/are in the lead? ○ Who is/are funding? ○ What expertise(s) is/are involved? <p><u>Operational nodes:</u> Afterwards, move & resize the clusters of activities in such a way, it reflects your ideal citizen science hub in your region.</p> <p>Summarize the preferable “profile” of your ideal Citizen Science Hub. Examples of profiles are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ “Lab” ○ “Project office” ○ “Competence center” ○ “Meeting place” ○ “Communication channel” ○ “Centralized platform” ○ other: <p>Complement the selected or self-made profile (a noun) with one or more adjectives reflecting the main values of your citizen science hub e.g., “Open door lab”</p> <p>Be prepared to share the profile of your ideal Citizen Science Hub in the plenary conclusions. And be prepared to fill in the following sentence: “The main stakeholders of our CSH are, and they will lose sleep when our Citizen Science Hub would stop to exist because....”</p>		
<p>11h45-12h00 15 min</p>	<p>Follow up (15 min) 4 summaries of profiles of the 4 CSH’s and 4 rights to exist: The main stakeholders of our CSH are... and they will lose sleep when our Citizen Science Hub would stop to exist because.... Slide with indication how the results of the workshops will be used in the follow-up tasks of INCENTIVE:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Governance and operating models in T2.2 ● M&E framework of T5.1 (link is provided in the Part 3 Mural) <p><i>PLENARY</i></p>		

Appendix II: Onboarding kit 22 September 2021

Co-creation workshop

Onboarding kit

Welcome to INCENTIVE!

We are delighted to welcome you to the INCENTIVE Co-creation Workshop as a key expert in fields relevant to Citizen Science. With this *Onboarding kit*, we aim to provide you with all the relevant information about the upcoming and last session on September 22, 2021. Please read this document carefully and feel free to contact us (see p.4) when facing unclarity!

INCENTIVE in a nutshell

INCENTIVE is a 3-year European project aiming to demonstrate the potential of citizen science through the **co-creation, establishment and assessment of Citizen Science Hubs (CSH) in four European universities:**

- University of Twente (NL)
- Autonomous University of Barcelona (ES)
- Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (GR)
- Vilnius Gediminas Technical University (LT)

You have been nominated by one of these universities. The project will accelerate the transition towards **more inclusive, open and democratic research involving academic researchers and citizens, professionals, experts from outside the university**. INCENTIVE aims to support research institutes on how to create and operate their own CSH with the aim to secure a democratic and collaborative way of doing research and setting research agendas. On [INCENTIVE](#) you can also register for the newsletter.

Curious to read more about Citizen Science? Have a look at the following essentials by the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA):

[The ECSA Characteristics of Citizen Science](#)

[The 10 principles of Citizen Science](#)

About the Co-creation workshop

Looking back

We are now boarding for the last and final session. In the first session, on June 16th, we focused on **Connect** (getting to know each other) & **Relate** (understanding each other's perspectives, discussing frictions and issues). Being the very first session, we needed to get to know each other and familiarise ourselves with the technology which caused some confusion which was only natural. A Mural board was used to support the first session: [link](#).

In the next sessions, on June 23rd, we first re-**Connected** as there were some new participants at the table) and then we dove into the content in **Understand & Frame** and **Imagine & Ideate**. We interpreted the prework outcomes (regional profiles, see below), adjusted where needed and moved to defining a framework for the respective CSH at one of the four universities. A second Mural board was used to support these sessions: [link](#).

Goals and results

The goal of the fourth and final session is to focus on the **Imagine & Ideate** parts of the Responsible Futuring approach (Fig 1). At the end of the session, we have co-defined the pivotal aspects of the governance and operating of your preferred CSH. This will be done through meaningful exercises in which you define the **values** of your citizen science hub, build future **scenarios** for them, and finally define the operational nodes of your CSH.

Responsible Futuring approach

At [DesignLab](#) – we are organising the workshop- the ambition is to bridge the gaps between society and science and open new avenues to tackle societal challenges – a vision that we share with INCENTIVE. We work together with societal stakeholders to generate responsible change for a future worth living during the research process. The goal is to make a positive impact on people's

daily lives and contribute to the development of technology and knowledge from the perspective of societal goals, challenges, and values of people. We do so by combining transdisciplinary working, responsible design and citizen involvement. We call it 'Responsible Futuring'.

For INCENTIVE, we apply the approach in a way that we incorporate it in a series of co-creation sessions. We will go through the specific phases of the approach and co-create the establishment of the CSH with the involved stakeholders. The phases are:

- i. In **Connect & Relate**, you introduce yourself to the other stakeholders of your region and take perspective of another with respect to the motives to be involved in citizen science.
- ii. In **Understand & Frame**, together with the other participants, you define a common frame on what citizen science is about and what not
- iii. In **Imagine & Ideate**, you work together on your preferred future CSH

In a later phase of INCENTIVE, we will look back and **Reflect & Reframe**.

Figure 1 Responsible Futuring for the Co-creation workshop

Pre-work

Prior to the sessions, we made workspaces in close collaboration with the four participating universities: follow this [link](#) to the first Mural board. Please note that this contextual information is not meant to be complete or set in stone - we just hope it gives you relevant background information of your region.

Do I need to prepare for the workshop?

Yes! Before the session on September 22, we request you to complete an individual exercise that will take you 15 minutes approximately. We invite you to reflect on important values (things that matter to you) while shaping the future of CSH. Join the online board we prepared for you and find on Mural the workspace of your university: follow this [link](#). You find the homework area on top of each workspace. Please complete the exercise by **September 20**.

INSTRUCTIONS HOMEWORK EXERCISE

Follow these three steps

Step 1: Pick two values In the homework area in Mural, pick from the list provided, pick two values that you consider important for your CSH. Drag the values from the provided list to the "visualizing values" area. One value for each template

Step 2: Provide answers to the following questions Respond, with your own words, to the following questions:

1. What does this value mean to you?
2. Why is it important?
3. What does it mean to your CSH?

Step 3: Visualize the value After providing answers to the questions, select an icon or a set of icons visualizing the value

Step 4: Share At the beginning of the session on September 22, you will share these values with others, and will be the foundation of the rest of the session

Do you need a concrete example? We have prepared one for you!

If you need a concrete example, have a look at the example we have prepared below. After completing the homework, you should have something like this for

Figure 2 Example of the homework exercise

Is this your first time participating? Then we ask you to fill in the **Informed consent** form so that we comply with the ethical requirements of the research that will be conducted alongside the establishment of the CSH. (See Appendix III)

What happens with the outcomes?

The outcomes of the Co-creation workshop are of vital importance to the next phases of INCENTIVE feeding the governance and operating models of each of the hubs and its envisaged activities as well as the pilots of each of the hubs. Moreover, the outcomes of this session will be analysed as input to the project's Monitoring and Evaluation framework.

Practicalities

Time, date & setting

The Co-creation workshop is broken down in four online sessions. The first three sessions took place in June and the final session will be in September. All sessions will be fully online, and we will make use of two digital applications: **Zoom** and **Mural**. In two appendices accompanying this *Onboarding kit*, we have provided instructions. Please make yourself familiar to both applications before the sessions start. It is advised to start Zoom 15 min prior to as there tend to be automated updates that may cause delay.

The session consists of limited plenary parts in which the goals and the expected outcomes will be discussed and regional-based exercises that bring together the stakeholders of the four regions to come to the best possible outcomes for each region. In these regional-based exercises, a **local host** and **table host** will ensure that the co-creation runs smoothly and that questions can be answered accordingly. It is possible that a guest from the consortium visits the region to observe.

CO-CREATION WORKSHOP SESSION IV

Date: Wednesday 22nd of September 2021
Times: 10:00-12:00 CEST; virtual doors open from 9:45
Zoom URL: [link](#)
Zoom meeting ID: 885 6657 5313
Zoom pass code: 979014
Mural board #3: [link](#)

Participants and observants

You have been nominated by your regional university as each of the four universities has nominated approx. 5 key stakeholders in their regional ecosystem that represent the quadrants of the Quadruple Helix: academia, government, private sector and civil society.

Partners from the project will join the session as *observers* to get direct access to the process and outcomes of the session that are relevant for their share of the project. The observers may not influence the co-creation process.

Questions, remarks or any other issues? Feel free to contact us!

Janine Swaak (j.swaak@utwente.nl, +31 622925459) will moderate the Co-creation workshop; **Maya van den Berg** (m.m.vandenberg@utwente.nl, +31 642198516) is INCENTIVE's programme manager; **Jorik Ordelmans** (j.ordelmans@student.utwente.nl) provides technical support.

The INCENTIVE consortium

University of Twente is a young, entrepreneurial research university where 3,200 scientists and professionals conduct pioneering research on nanotechnology, ICT, biomedical technology and technical medicine, engineering, governance and behavioural sciences and geo-information / earth observation sciences. Founded in 1961 in Enschede, the Netherlands, the UT stands for high tech with a human touch. INCENTIVE is coordinated by UTs DesignLab.

Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB) was founded in 1968, with four principles of autonomy: freedom to select teaching staff, admission available to all students (but with a limited number), freedom to create its own study plans and freedom to administrate the University's capital. It is therefore a young university, but in its short history it has moved forward at a rapid pace. The UAB is an institution that demonstrates its commitment to society by contributing in two main areas: knowledge and innovation. The UAB is aiming to transform into one of the most important scientific and technological poles of the Mediterranean.

Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH) is the largest academic institution in Greece and one of the largest in South-eastern Europe covering all disciplines and scientific fields from science and arts to humanities and

divinity, medicine and technology. AUTH is known as the most interdisciplinary university of Greece with a wide range of services in basic and applied research, mainly in the fields of engineering, environment, information technology, psychology and health, humanities, education, history and languages, social and economic sciences.

Vilnius Gediminas Technical University (VGTU) is the leader among the higher education institutions of technological sciences in Lithuania strongly focusing on the European Research Area. Established in 1956, VGTU has over 10 400 students and 960 academic staff in 10 faculties 13 research institutes, 3 research centers, 23 research laboratories.

Competence Center – Citizen Science CC-CS (often called Citizen Science Center Zurich) is a joint initiative of the University of Zurich and of the Swiss Federal Institute of Technology, ETH Zurich. Created in 2017, its purpose is to enable researchers and citizens to create and conduct Citizen Science research collaborations that produce excellent science. Being supported by academia, the Center focuses on supporting academic-quality processes and results and prioritize those activities and projects that maximize the collaboration between citizens and scientists in all phases of the research process.

SDA Bocconi is the School of Management of Università Commerciale “L. Bocconi” and has been creating and sharing knowledge since 1971. The Schools commitment to research and education has enabled it, over the years, to contribute significantly to the development of many industries, both in Italy and abroad. SDA Bocconi considers its people as the main resource in pursuing its mission. It invests in their personal development and gives them the opportunity to carry out meaningful roles in its governance activities.

Q-PLAN International Advisors PC is an innovation and management consulting company that possesses valuable know-how and expertise in the

design, management and co-ordination of policy studies, research projects and support actions. Q-PLAN is also a regional market leader in the development and implementation of auditing and Management Systems (e.g., ISO 9001, ISO 14001, ISO 22000, ISO 27001, etc.), with more than 1.700 certified private and public-sector clients from all business sectors.

White Research is a social research SME specializing in consumer behaviour, market analysis, and innovation management in key sectors including ICT, Energy, Health, Transport, Circular and Smart Cities, as well as in other related sectors and sub-fields. The company addresses business strategy, policy, market, and user related issues through an array of diverse analytic tools. WR specializes in the design and implementation of stakeholder engagement strategies.

Since 2013, **the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA)** has evolved from an informal network of citizen science practitioners to an influential association that supports and advocates for public participation in science, in Europe. A non-profit organisation (“eingetragener Verein”) registered under German law, it is currently hosted at the Museum for Natural History in Berlin, Leibniz Institute for Evolution and Biodiversity Research, Germany. The Executive Board is assisted in the governance of the organisation by a Board of Directors.

APPENDIX I How to work with Zoom?

Step 1: Clicking on the Zoom link on p4 will automatically take you to the correct session (you can also click it prior to the session). You will then get a screen that looks something like the one shown below. You can choose to enter the session via the Zoom web application (requires installation) or in the browser. You do the latter by clicking on "join from web browser" (see below).

Step 2: If you have a Zoom account, you will go directly to the meeting. If not, you will be asked to enter a name (see screen below). If all goes well the meeting password is already filled in, if not then this is provided at the Practicalities section. After these are correct, click on "Join".

Step 3: You will now get a screen as shown below, with "Join Audio by Computer" in it, click on it. You may get a pop-up from your web browser asking if you want to give Zoom permission to use your microphone, click allow. From that moment on you can hear us and vice versa, we can hear you.

Step 4: When you are in the session your webcam is automatically turned off, you can turn it on by clicking "Start Video". Again, your web browser may ask you if you want to give permission to use your webcam, click allow here as well.

Step 5: Ready! You can see and hear everyone, and vice versa we can hear you. Do you want to change anything in your audio or video settings, for example use a different microphone? You can do this directly in the meeting using the two marked arrows in the image below. The Zoom functionality that we are going to use will be shown during the workshop.

APPENDIX II How to work with Mural?

Step 1: Click on the [link](#) to go to INCENTIVE's playing area in Mural that was specifically prepared for the session on September 22, 2021.

If you have a Mural account (not required), you will enter the environment as yourself. If you do not have an account, you will automatically become an 'anonymous koala' or 'anonymous bear'. As an anonymous user you will have access to all functionalities.

Step 2: Done! You are now in Mural, which should look something like the image below.

Functionalities in Mural you will be using frequently:

- Zoom out to see the total overview of the Mural (right corner, select move mode)
- zoom in to read (right corner, select move mode)
- create new post-it: you can 'copy' & 'paste' existing post-it's the way you are used to copy and paste (select menu in the top left)
- write post-it: if you double click a post-it, you can start writing on it

APPENDIX III Informed consent form to INCENTIVE Co-creation workshop

Who we are: We are the DesignLab of the University of Twente and we are contacting you in the framework of INCENTIVE, a project funded by the European Union under the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation. A detailed description of how INCENTIVE handles personal data is presented in the project's Privacy Policy

Project: INCENTIVE - Establishing Citizen Science Hubs in European Research Performing and Funding Organisations to drive institutional change and ground Responsible Research and Innovation in society (GA Number 101005330).

Partner:

Organisation name: DesignLab
 Address: Hengelosestraat 500
 Phone: +31534892079
 E-mail: designlab@utwente.nl

Responsible persons:

Dr. Maya van den Berg, programme manager, m.m.vandenberg@utwente.nl
 Dr. Sabine Wildevuur, director, sabine.wildevuur@utwente.nl
 Dr. Cristina Zaga, researcher

What do we need from you?

We were hoping you could participate in a co-creation workshop carried out by INCENTIVE. The workshops will help the INCENTIVE to produce future scenarios of Citizen Science Hubs. It will help us gather scientific and practical insights about how to structure the operation and governance of Citizen Science Hubs in Europe. Eventually, this will provide us with fresh insights that will help us tailor the Citizen Science Hub of each RPFO and grasp better the specifics of the institutional changes that need to be implemented in each RPFO to ground RRI within their regional innovation ecosystem.

We plan to audio-video record the workshops to document the process and outcomes thereof

To effectively conduct this interview, we need to process some of your personal data:

- Some basic demographic (e.g., age, nationality)
- Your professional info (organisation, job position, field of expertise);

- Your opinion on the subject matter
- The outcomes of the discussion you will have in the workshop

Why do we need your data & what will we do with them?

We need your data to contact you to plan and carry out the workshop and to resolve any ambiguities, questions and other issues that may arise after and as a result of the workshops. We also need your data to assess the approach of the workshop, focusing on barriers and enablers for co-creation. The project deliverables that will be derived by the interview will not include your personal data or any other information that will identify you. We will anonymize the data and destroy them after five years.

We will share your data with the other INCENTIVE project partners involved in this task and who will participate in the drafting of the relevant deliverables. We are also obliged to grant access to your data to:

- EU officials such as our Project Officer for purposes related to project's evaluation
- EU agencies and other authorities for projects

How can you withdraw your consent?

You should know that you can withdraw your consent at any time by communicating either on the phone or by email with the responsible persons listed on the previous page. With regards to the informational messages and newsletters you can always opt-out by simply clicking the link "Unsubscribe" or something similar included at the end of all the relevant messages.

#	CONSENT SUBJECT	PLEASE TICK
1	My participation in a recorded workshop that will be carried out by INCENTIVE to understand the process and its outcomes	
2	My participation in future activities of INCENTIVE	

Name

Date.....

Signature

Please sign and submit this form to m.m.vandenberg@utwente.nl

Appendix III: Mural Boards of the Co-Creation Workshop

Available online in full detail at the following webpages:

[INCENTIVE Playground 1 - 16 June 2021](#)

<https://app.mural.co/t/designlabuniveristyoftwente4963/m/designlabuniveristyoftwente4963/1620830217768/42a0e816bd091c6f84fc4d7b7c955d1b35ba87e5>

[INCENTIVE Playground 2 - 23 June 2021](#)

<https://app.mural.co/t/designlabuniveristyoftwente4963/m/designlabuniveristyoftwente4963/1624299194986/d3353ef741548f451c54dde3827dc5a0082d6b5e>

[INCENTIVE Playground 3 - 22 September 2021](#)

<https://app.mural.co/t/designlabuniveristyoftwente4963/m/designlabuniveristyoftwente4963/1628058153073/53741ba2d6c0cc36d06b7fd7b0ff9e5ab9584e7c>

ABOUT THE PROJECT

INCENTIVE aims to demonstrate the potential of citizen science through the co-creation, establishment and assessment of CSHs in four EU Universities: University of Twente (NL), Autonomous University of Barcelona (ES), Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (EL) and Vilnius Gediminas Technical University (LT).

By doing so, the project accelerates the transition of these institutions to more inclusive, open and democratic innovation and scientific governance, under the principles of Responsible Research and Innovation. The project seeks to deliver a legacy to European and international research institutes on how to create and operate their own Hub with the aim to secure a sustainable future.

COORDINATOR

UNIVERSITEIT TWENTE (DesignLab)

PARTNERS

UNIVERSITEIT TWENTE (DesignLab)
www.utwente.nl/en/designlab

UNIVERSIDAD AUTONOMA DE BARCELONA
www.uab.es

ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS
www.auth.gr

VILNIAUS GEDIMINO TECHNIKOS UNIVERSITETAS
vilniustech.lt

UNIVERSITAT ZURICH
www.uzh.ch

UNIVERSITA COMMERCIALE LUIGI BOCCONI
www.unibocconi.eu

Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS
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